

HUMANITIES DATA INQUIRY

Exploring Data Issues in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage

STRATEGY

DISCOVER

- Shared knowledge
- Humanities Data Practices
- Data Variation

DEMONSTRATE

- Document common problems and solutions
- Collaborate on shared problems

MOBILIZE

- Common understandings
- Best practices
- Shared incentives

PARTICIPATE

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The Humanities Data Inquiry (HDI) is a community of practice (CoP) working to move the needle on data in humanities and cultural heritage (HCH) through inquiry, knowledge sharing, collaborative problem solving, clarifying best practices, and innovation.

Funded by a SSHRC partnership grant, HDI will convene regular opportunities for those working with HCH data to 'think together' about the unique features of humanities and cultural heritage data, and to collaborate on ways to re-imagine and design research data tools and infrastructures.

HDI is organized around community dialogue, such as reading and discussion groups, community and guest presentations, and roundtables; original research, documenting the variety of data practices in humanities scholarship; and opportunities to collaborate on common problems.

The emergence of 'Big Data' in the STEM fields has strongly privileged research data management (RDM) models and use-cases that are skewed towards data and large data sets generated through observation and experimentation. By contrast, HCH data is extremely varied, often involving combinations of data that are 'Small,' involving representation of real-world objects; 'Thick,' richly curated and contextualized research objects; and 'Slow,' where the definition and analysis of can continue for generations. When this data meets contemporary RDM infrastructure, the results are often data products that are siloed, invisible or difficult to access; unnecessarily expensive to produce and maintain; in danger of premature loss or obsolescence to researchers and the wider community. HDI aims to address this by rethinking HCH data practices from the ground up.